

Formulation and Characterization of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) for Enhancement of Oral Bioavailability of Atorvastatin Calcium

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) were formulated by the method of emulsification followed by sonication. In this method, NLCs were formulated by the use of solid lipid, liquid lipid and the surfactant Poloxamer 188 using high speed homogenizer. The 32 factorial design was used to prepare the nine batches of Atorvastatin Calcium loaded NLCs. The batches were optimized based on the particle size, zeta potential and percent drug entrapment efficiency. The % drug entrapment efficiency of all the nine batches were found in the range of 59.12 ± 0.12 % to 89.10 ± 0.20 %. Thus, the highest drug entrapment was found in batch F4. The F4 batch was the optimum batch based on optimum particle size, zeta potential, Polydispersity index and the % drug entrapment efficiency. The first seven batches of NLCs were shadow dried to convert the NLC suspension into dry powder form of NLCs. The NLCs equivalent to therapeutic dose from all the seven batches were incorporated into tablet dosage form. The formulated tablets were evaluated for post compression parameters. The tablets from F4 formulation were considered optimized based on in vitro % drug release studies. The % drug release from the batch F4 was found to be 91.51 % at the end of 12 hours. The optimized batch of NLCs tablet was compared with marketed tablet for in vitro release study. The release of marketed tablet at the end of 12 hours was found to be 57.51 %

Keywords: Nanostructured Lipid Carriers, Oral Bioavailability, Atorvastatin Calcium

INTRODUCTION

Modified lipid nanoparticles, also termed as nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), came into picture in early 2000 to modulate the physical state and drug loading capacity of SLNs. NLCs possess unique characteristics and are formulated using a combination of solid and liquid lipids where less ordered structures are produced, which offer the firmer inclusion of the drug molecules within. It has been consistently reported that the increased entrapment efficiency in NLCs is attributed to the structural parity of two lipids in NLCs that results in imperfections in their structure while solidification provides higher space for accommodation of drugs.

Also, the higher entrapment efficiency is due to higher solubility of drugs in liquid lipids in comparison to solid lipids. Higher payload capacity along with long shelf storage stability thus makes NLCs as an advanced carrier in comparison to other conventional lipid-based systems. Further, NLCs have the feasibility of incorporating both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. In addition to this, they may provide sustained release of drugs and target them to the site of action. Various studies have proven that this nano platform has shown improvement in oral bioavailability of drugs via promoting their intestinal absorption. This system has also shed a light of hope for treatment of chronic diseases due to its modulation with drug efficacy and sustained for longer periods.^[1]

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Drug Profile of Atorvastatin calcium:**Chemical structure:****Chemical formula:** C₆₆H₆₈CaF₂N₄O₁₀

Atorvastatin Calcium, is a lipid-lowering drug included in the statin class of medications. By inhibiting the endogenous production of cholesterol in the liver, statins lower abnormal cholesterol and lipid levels, and ultimately reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases.

MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENTS

Atorvastatin Calcium was received as gift sample from Ajanta Pharma Ltd. Aurangabad. Compritol 888 ATO and Capryol PGMC were received from Gattefosse India Pvt. Ltd. whereas Poloxamer 188 was obtained from BASF India Pvt. Ltd. as gift samples.

High speed homogenizer with the make of T 25 digital ULTRA-TURRAX-IKA, Bangalore, India. Was used for high shearing rates to obtain NLCs followed by sonication for rearrangements. Malvern Zeta sizer Nano ZS90 with the make of Malvern instrument Limited, UK was used for characterization of NLCs.

Methods of formulation of NLCs**Formulation of Atorvastatin Calcium loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs):**

- The Atorvastatin loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) preparation was made by high shear homogenization by the instrument high speed homogenizer (HSG) (T 25 digital

ULTRA-TURRAX-IKA, Bangalore, India) followed by sonication.

- In this method, the lipid phase was prepared by melting the lipids at temperature ten degrees Celsius above its melting point and to it drug was added. It was kept at same temperature until it becomes optically clear.
- Simultaneously, the aqueous phase was prepared separately by dissolving Poloxamer 188 with distilled water and heated to same temperature as that of the lipid phase.
- The aqueous phase was dispersed to the lipid phase and the mixture was subjected to homogenization at 17000 rpm.
- The formulation was kept for sonication for 40 minutes.
- The prepared formulation was then stored at 4 degree Celsius [2, 3].

Table 7.2: Design of Experiment for NLCs of Atorvastatin Calcium

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Atorvastatin Calcium (gram)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Compritol 888 ATO (gram)	5	5	5	7	7	7	9	9	9
Capryol PGMC (gram)	3	4	6	3	4	6	3	4	6
Poloxamer 188 (%)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

8.6. Characterization of formulated NLCs:

1. Particle size and Polydispersity index:

The formulated nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) dispersion is evaluated for its particle size in nano meter by using Malvern zeta sizer Nano ZS 90 instrument to get optimum results the particle size should be in the range of 200-300nm.

Polydispersity index give the estimation about particle size distribution. It is also determined by Malvern zeta sizer.

2. Zeta potential:

Zeta potential is an indication of the repulsive force that is present in nanoparticles and is a key factor in predicting the long term stability of colloidal dispersion system. In general, particles can be dispersed stably when absolute value of zeta potential is greater than 30 mV due to electric repulsion between particles.

3. % Entrapment efficiency:

The entrapment efficiency is determined by centrifugation method. A volume of 1.5 ml of drug loaded sample was centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 45 minutes. The supernatant was collected and appropriate dilutions was made with phosphate buffer

of pH 6.8 and analysed spectrophotometrically at 246 nm.

The % entrapment efficiency was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total amount of drug} - \text{Total amount of unbound drug}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

4. Short term stability studies:

The stability studies were conducted according to ICH guidelines. Samples were stored in glass vials for 30 days at 4°C and at room temperature (25 ± 2°C). After 7, 15 and 30 days samples were evaluated for change in form and appearance.

8.8 Development of Atorvastatin Calcium loaded NLC containing tablets:

After the development of Atorvastatin Calcium loaded nanostructured lipid carrier (AT-NLC) it is incorporated into tablet dosage form. The NLC powder from first seven batches was formulated into tables. The tablets was formulated by direct compression method. NLCs equivalent to specific amount of Atorvastatin Calcium along with excipients such as Avicel, Magnesium stearate, and talc was used. The formulated tablets should have all the optimum characteristics. The composition of seven batches is tabulated as below:

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
NLC powder equivalent to 20 mg Atorvastatin (mg)	25.45	23.06	33.82	22.44	26.18	24.33	30.36
Avicel (mg)	168.55	170.94	160.18	171.56	167.82	169.67	163.64
Magnesium stearate(mg)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc(mg)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Evaluation of atorvastatin Calcium loaded NLC tablets:

The following evaluations of tablets were performed:

1. General Appearance: The tablets were examined for the shape of the tablet and was observed by keeping the tablets in light.

2. Weight variation test: The tablets were selected randomly from each batch and weighed individually to check for weight variation. As per U.S Pharmacopoeia 2009 a little variation is allowed in the weight of a tablet. The following percentage deviation in weight variation is allowed as shown in the below

table. In all formulations, the tablet weighed is 300 mg, hence 7.5 percentage deviations are allowed.

Average weight of a tablet	Percentage deviation
130 mg or less	10
>130 mg and <324 mg	7.5
324 mg or more	5

3. Thickness test: Thickness of tablets from each formulation were measured by using Vernier callipers by picking the five tablets randomly. The values are almost uniform in specific method.

4. Hardness test: Hardness test was performed by using Pfizer tester. Hardness was maintained to be within 6.0 kg/cm² to 8.0 kg/cm². The lower standard deviation values indicated that the hardness of all the formulations were almost uniform in specific method and possess good mechanical strength with sufficient hardness.

5. Friability test: The percentage friability was determined to be below 1% for all the prepared batches which is an indication of good mechanical resistance of the tablet.

8.10 Comparative study of NLC tablets with marketed formulation: The dissolution study was

performed to compare the drug loaded NLC tablets with the marketed tablet Storvas 20.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation Studies

The aim of preformulation studies is to investigate the physical and chemical properties of a drug substance. The selected drug Atorvastatin Calcium was subjected for investigation of physical characterization parameters such as:

- Organoleptic properties
- Melting point
- UV-visible spectra
- Solubility
- FT-IR spectra

Organoleptic properties

Sr. No.	Properties	Inferences
1.	Colour	White
2.	Form	Crystalline
3.	Taste	Slightly bitter
4.	Oudor	Oudorless

Melting Point

The melting point of a substance is the temperature at which the solid phase gets converted to liquid phase. The melting point determination implies the purity of

drug. Melting point of Atorvastatin Calcium was determined by capillary tube method and was found to be quite similar to the reported melting point as shown in Table 9.2

Drug	Reference M.P.	Observed M.P.
Atorvastatin Calcium	159 °C	159 °C

The melting point of Atorvastatin Calcium was found to be 159 °C which is in the range of the pure drug. Hence, drug sample was free from any type of impurities

UV Spectroscopy

Determination of absorption maxima in methanol

Ultraviolet absorption spectroscopy was used for quantitative analysis of Atorvastatin Calcium. The drug was dissolved in methanol at a concentration of 4 µg/ml, and was scanned in the range of 200-400 nm.

The analytically useful wavelength maximum (λ_{max}) of atorvastatin calcium in methanol was approximately 246 nm.

Name of drug		Absorption maxima	
Atorvastatin Calcium	Observed	Reference	
	246 nm	246 nm	

Preparation of standard curve of Atorvastatin Calcium

Table 9.4: Calibration curve of Atorvastatin Calcium

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (nm)
0	0
2	0.2074
4	0.3790
6	0.5430
8	0.7099
10	0.8162
12	0.9882

Figure: 9.1 Standard calibration curve of Atorvastatin in methanol (λ_{max} = 246 nm)

Table 9.5: Result of regression analysis of UV method

Statistical Parameters	Results
λ_{max}	246nm
Regression equation (y=mx+c)	Y=0.0806x+0.037
Slope(m)	0.0806
Intercept (C)	0.037
Regression coefficient (R^2)	0.9944

Solubility studies

Solubility of drug in various solvents, were carried out in order to screen for the components to be used for formulation development. Analysis of the drug was carried out on UV Spectrophotometer at 246 nm.

Table 9.6: Solubility studies of Atorvastatin Calcium for different solvents

Name of solvent	Solubility
Methanol	Freely soluble
Ethanol	Freely soluble
Distilled water	Insoluble
Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8	Slightly soluble

FTIR studies

Fig.9.2 FTIR spectra of Atorvastatin Calcium

The IR spectrum of pure drug (Figure no 2) was found to be similar to the standard spectrum of Atorvastatin calcium. The spectrum of the Atorvastatin calcium shows the following functional groups at their frequencies:

Table 9.7 Frequency at functional group

Cm-1 Group	Group
3364	O–H Stretching
3320	RCO-OH Stretching
1338	S=O Asymmetric
1963	C=N/ C=O

Fig 9.3 FTIR spectra of Compritol 888 ATO

Fig 9.4 FTIR spectra of Poloxamer 188

Table 9.8 characterization of NLCs

Formulation	Mean particle size \pm SD (nm)	Polydispersity index (PDI)	Zeta potential (mV)
F1	203.5 \pm 2.51	0.298 \pm 0.054	-27.6 \pm 0.44
F2	273.3 \pm 1.52	0.359 \pm 0.046	-43.28 \pm 1.62
F3	146.4 \pm 3.05	0.399 \pm 0.032	-50.6 \pm 0.46
F4	289.3 \pm 3.60	0.344 \pm 0.034	-34.5 \pm 0.90
F5	197.6 \pm 2.10	0.471 \pm 0.026	-20.5 \pm 1.50
F6	226.6 \pm 2.60	0.437 \pm 0.045	-32.4 \pm 0.40
F7	337.7 \pm 2.64	0.485 \pm 0.047	-43.28 \pm 1.62
F8	323.9 \pm 2.08	0.381 \pm 0.052	-50.6 \pm 0.46
F9	183.2 \pm 3.04	0.288 \pm 0.044	-25.1 \pm 1.70

In FTIR spectra of pure drug and FTIR spectra of NLC formulation, similar group are present. Hence

there is no interaction between drug and polymer means they are compatible to each other.

9.2 Characterization of nanostructured lipid carriers

The formulated Nanostructured lipid carriers was characterized for particle size, Polydispersity index

and zeta potential. The values are expressed in following table: Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (mean \pm SD) (n=3)

Table 9.9 % Entrapment efficiency of NLCs:

Formulation code	% Entrapment efficiency (%)
F1	78.56 \pm 0.62
F2	86.70 \pm 0.20
F3	59.12 \pm 0.12
F4	89.10 \pm 0.20
F5	76.37 \pm 0.12
F6	82.20 \pm 0.38
F7	65.80 \pm 0.42
F8	62.80 \pm 0.50
F9	72.03 \pm 0.42

Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (mean \pm SD) (n=3) The batch F4 has shown maximum % drug entrapment of 89.10 \pm 0.20 % and it was the optimized batch.

In vitro release profile result:

The release of drug from NLCs was studied by comparing the drug release with pure drug

suspension. The pure drug release profile showed ~ 53.62 % drug release in 12 hrs, the whereas the optimized NLC formulation showed drug release about 88.78% which indicates increase in bioavailability of NLCs. The comparative *in vitro* drug release profile and optimized formulation F4 and pure drug suspension was shown as below.

Table. 9.10 *In vitro* drug release by NLC batch F4 and pure drug suspension

Time (hrs)	F4 NLC batch (%)	Pure drug suspension (%)
0	0	0
2	22.76	18.32
4	43.56	21.66
6	54.33	25.09
8	78.68	38.47
10	81.53	44.37
12	88.78	53.62

Figure: 9.6 Comparative *in vitro* drug release profile of optimized formulation F4 and pure drug suspension

9.4 Evaluation of formulated tablets: The formulated tablets were of optimum shape and size. Tablets were subjected to various evaluation

parameters including weight variation, tablet hardness, friability, and thickness, and in-vitro drug release studies. These results are tabulated as follows.

Table 9.11 Evaluation of seven batches of NLCs loaded tablets.

Formulation code	Weight variation	Thickness (mm ± SD)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)
F1	308.25 ± 0.09	3.7 ± 0.09	7.3 ± 0.04	0.61 ± 0.07
F2	291.10 ± 0.07	3.9 ± 0.02	7.8 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.02
F3	307.21 ± 0.03	4.0 ± 0.07	8.0 ± 0.07	0.58 ± 0.03
F4	295.15 ± 0.04	3.8 ± 0.04	6.5 ± 0.04	0.72 ± 0.01
F5	297.32 ± 0.03	4.7 ± 0.03	6.8 ± 0.08	0.66 ± 0.03
F6	305.15 ± 0.06	3.8 ± 0.09	7.1 ± 0.03	0.71 ± 0.09
F7	298.51 ± 0.03	4.1 ± 0.01	6.1 ± 0.05	0.44 ± 0.03

Table 9.12 In vitro % drug release study of NLCs loaded tablets

Time in Hour	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	10.69	9.63	11.31	13.12	12.15	13.62	15.32
2	15.23	16.21	14.56	15.18	14.32	19.52	19.32
3	21.61	19.32	17.32	21.32	22.51	25.32	31.51
4	28.32	25.32	24.51	28.51	25.32	31.52	34.23
5	38.14	39.51	28.51	32.61	33.32	36.39	38.51
6	40.23	43.71	31.82	38.51	39.72	49.32	43.23
7	45.15	49.32	36.51	43.61	45.32	53.32	47.31
8	51.32	53.73	43.32	53.32	53.72	61.92	51.62
9	57.83	58.32	49.51	63.51	57.32	67.72	63.62
10	63.75	64.71	53.51	77.53	63.32	69.39	70.32
11	69.15	68.32	58.32	83.32	79.51	71.52	76.79
12	72.16	69.51	63.85	91.51	83.92	81.51	83.51

Figure 9.7: comparative study of in vitro % drug release study of NLC tablet batch F1 to F3

The optimized batch of NLCs loaded tablet from first seven batches of NLCs formulations was the F4 batch from the above dissolution profile.

Figure 9.8: Comparative in vitro drug release study of NLC tablet batch F4 to F7

The batch F4 has shown maximum % drug release of 91.51%

Figure 9.9 Comparative in vitro % drug release of batch F4 and marketed tablet

The NLC tablet has shown better release pattern than the marketed tablet, hence it has shown greater bioavailability as shown in above figure 9.9

9.5 Short term stability studies results of NLCs:

The samples were stored in closed glass vials for 30 days at 4°C and at room temperature (25 ± 2°C). After 7, 15 and 30 days samples were evaluated for change in form and appearance. No change in form and appearance was found.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) were successfully formulated by the method of emulsification by the instrument high speed

homogenization followed by sonication. In this method, NLCs were formulated by the use of solid lipid, liquid lipid and the surfactant Poloxamer 188. The developed formulation possesses optimum particle size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, % entrapment efficiency. The *in vitro* drug release studies from NLCs has shown optimum release pattern compared to pure drug suspension. Out of nine batches of NLCs suspension, the first seven batches of NLCs powder were formulated into tablets successfully and batch F4 has shown optimum % drug release.

The F4 batch of NLCs formulated into tablet was compared with marketed tablet for *in vitro* drug release studies the former has shown enhanced drug

release than the later. Therefore, NLCs incorporated tablets have shown enhancement in bioavailability than the conventional formulations.

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